

The Study of Criminal Motivation and Crime Prevention of Offenders

Dr. Jun Zhang^{1*} and Dr. Ao Zhang²

¹College of Education, Sehan University, Jeollanam-do, 650106, Republic of Korea

²School of Computer Science and Communication Engineering, Jiangsu University, Zhenjiang, 212013, Jiangsu, China

Abstract

Individuals' motivation to commit crime is often influenced by a confluence of factors such as mental health, emotional needs, economic status, social environment and family background. In addition, social factors such as social inequality, poverty, unemployment and social exclusion also play an important role in the formation of criminal motivation. An in-depth study of offenders' motivation can not only reveal the root causes of criminal behavior, but also provide a theoretical basis for the development of more effective crime prevention strategies and corrective measures. Future research should further explore the interactions between criminal motivation and social environment and cultural background to provide society with more comprehensive crime prevention and control countermeasures.

Keywords: Criminals; Crime Motivation; Crime Prevention

Introduction

Criminal motivation not only reflects the intrinsic drive of individuals to commit criminal acts, but also reveals the intertwined influences of social, psychological and cultural factors. An in-depth exploration of offenders' motivation to commit crimes can provide theoretical support and practical guidance for crime prevention, intervention, and the improvement of the criminal justice system [4].

Early criminological theories, such as the classical school, emphasized the rational choice of committing crimes, arguing that criminals committed crimes after a rational weighing of costs and benefits [5]. However, multidisciplinary research in sociology, psychology, and biology has shown that an individual's motivation to commit a crime is often influenced by a variety of factors, which include the individual's psychological characteristics, emotional impulses, family environment, and social background [13]. When individuals are in environments such as poverty, unemployment, and lack of educational opportunities, individuals often face great social pressure, and this pressure may induce them to change their situation through criminal behavior. In addition, family environment is also considered to be an important factor in influencing the motivation to commit crimes. Domestic violence, unhealthy parent-child relationships, and dysfunctional families may all contribute to an individual's motivation to commit a crime [15].

Definition and Classification of Criminal Motive

Criminal motivation refers to the psychological driving factor for individuals to commit criminal acts, which reflects the internal desires, needs and goals held by the subject of the behavior in the process of committing a crime. Criminal motivation is usually regarded as the root cause of crime occurrence, which not only explains why individuals choose to commit criminal acts, but also reveals the deep-seated psychological mechanism of behavior occurrence. Scholars of crime theory classify criminal motives from different theoretical perspectives, mainly including multi-dimensional divisions according to the nature of the motive, the source of the motive, and the purpose of the crime.

First of all, according to the division of the nature of criminal motives, scholars usually divide criminal motives into several types such as economic motives, emotional motives and self-actualization motives. Economic motivation is one of the most common motives in crime, such as theft, fraud, drug trafficking and other behaviors mostly originated from the individual's need for

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*Correspondence:

Dr. Jun Zhang, School of Business Administration, Tourism College of Zhejiang, Hangzhou, China & College of Education, Sehan University, Jeollanam-do, 650106, Republic of Korea,
E-mail: zhangjunahnu@163.com

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money or material [14]. Emotional motivation, on the other hand, involves individuals choosing to seek emotional catharsis or revenge by committing criminal acts when they are in emotional conflict or when their emotional needs are not met. Revenge crimes, violent behavior that occurs as a result of emotional disputes usually fall into this category. Self-actualization motivation, on the other hand, involves individuals realizing their self-worth or proving themselves through criminal behavior. For example, some extremists may express their loyalty to a certain politics or ideology through extreme behavior [7].

Secondly, according to the psychological division of the source of motivation, criminal motivation can be divided into several categories such as need satisfaction, emotional impulse and personality trait drive. Needs fulfillment motives are usually manifested as individuals choosing criminal behavior due to unsatisfied physiological, psychological, or social needs, such as poverty, unemployment, and social exclusion, which often prompt individuals to satisfy their basic life needs or gain social acceptance through illegal means [3]. Emotional impulse motivation, on the other hand, is more related to an individual's emotional fluctuations and impulsive behavior. When individuals lose their minds in emotional states such as anger, jealousy, shame, and fear, they may commit violent or other criminal acts. For example, domestic violence, love murder, and other types of crimes usually stem from strong emotional impulses. Personality trait-driven crime motives, on the other hand, are closely related to an individual's psychological traits and personality defects, such as antisocial personality and borderline personality, which may lead to increased impulsivity and aggressiveness [6].

Thirdly, according to the different divisions of criminal purposes, criminal motives can be categorized into utilitarian motives, retaliatory motives and expressive motives. Utilitarian motivation for crime is that the offender obtains financial benefits or other forms of rewards through criminal behavior. Most crimes such as theft, fraud and drug trafficking fall into this category. Retaliatory criminal motivation, on the other hand, is when criminal behavior occurs out of an individual's dissatisfaction and anger toward another person or a group of people, with the goal of retaliation or revenge through criminal behavior. For example, domestic violence, emotionally violent crimes, and aggressive crimes due to social hatred are all retaliatory motive driven behaviors [9]. Expressive criminal motivation, on the other hand, is when an individual expresses a certain emotion, political stance, or social dissatisfaction through criminal behavior. For example, some extremists convey their political or ideological demands through acts of terrorism, or violence in some social movements is used to oppose unjust social systems.

Factors influencing Criminal Motivation

The intrinsic motivation that influences individuals to commit criminal acts includes both psychological and social aspects, and in general, psychological factors tend to play a key role. For example, individuals with antisocial personality disorder tend to lack empathy and moral judgment, and are prone to impulsivity and aggression, personality traits that may lead them to choose criminal behavior in the face of temptation or conflict [8]. In addition to this, the social environment and economic factors can also play an important influence. Poverty, unemployment, low education level, and social inequality are all important social background factors for criminal motivation, while economic hardship often prompts individuals to satisfy their basic survival needs or pursue higher material enjoyment

through illegal means, especially among low-income groups, where economic pressure may lead to criminal behavior such as theft, fraud, and drug trafficking [16].

Family background is likewise an important factor in the formation of criminal motivation. Breakdowns in the family environment, discordant parent-child relationships, and the lack of an effective family support system can have a profound effect on an individual's psychological development and behavioral patterns. Dysfunctional families, especially violent family environments, parental divorce or neglect, may cause individuals to develop wrong values and behavioral patterns in their formative years, thus increasing their risk of moving towards delinquency. Especially in the adolescent stage, the family plays a significant role in shaping values and behaviors, and if the family lacks education and guidance or is filled with violence and criminal behaviors, adolescents may be prone to develop criminal motives in the absence of correct social cognition [10].

Effective Ways to Prevent Crime

The core objective of crime prevention is to reduce the occurrence of criminal behavior through effective measures and to maintain social order and public safety. There are various effective ways to prevent crime, involving psychological intervention, social policy, education and guidance, and legal means.

First, a sound and complete psychological intervention mechanism should be established. Early psychological identification and psychological intervention can effectively reduce the risk of crime due to psychological problems [12]. Psychological intervention during adolescence is especially important, as this period is a critical stage for the initial formation of individual values and behavioral patterns, but this transformation often brings a lot of psychological distress to individuals, such as anxiety, depression, etc. If psychological counseling and behavioral therapy are received at this time, it can help adolescents establish a healthy coping mechanism, thus preventing them from adopting extreme behaviors [1].

Second, establish a social welfare equalization system. When disadvantaged groups feel excluded or unfairly treated in society, they may express their dissatisfaction or access social welfare resources through criminal behavior. Therefore, the establishment of a fair social welfare policy and income distribution system, and the provision of employment opportunities can effectively alleviate the pressure of disadvantaged groups and reduce the motivation to commit crimes brought about by social inequality [2]. In addition, by establishing a more just and inclusive social structure, social exclusion can be reduced, thus reducing inter-group conflict and crime.

Finally, a humanized justice system should be improved. The law should not only sanction criminal behavior, but also provide society with an effective framework for crime prevention through legislation and policy formulation. Specifically, through the establishment of a sound legal system, law enforcement is strengthened to deter potential criminals and reduce the likelihood of crime [11]. At the same time, the justice system should focus on the correction and re-socialization of offenders, and help offenders reintegrate into society through incarceration, community correction, and vocational training to reduce the recidivism rate.

Conclusion

Criminal activities directly disrupt the social order and make the

daily life of the people threatened. In order to control the effects of criminal activities continue to grow, the government and security sector need to spend social resources to respond and deal with it, such as police force, judiciary, prison facilities and so on. However, crime prevention programs must be more balanced and comprehensive. While effectively preventing and controlling crime, the fundamental rights and freedoms of citizens must be safeguarded. At the same time, society should pay more attention to crime prevention from the perspectives of education, psychological intervention and social support, so as to reduce the generation of criminal motivation at source.

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